

COMPUTER SCIENCES

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METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING "SCHEME OPERATORS" IN THE INFORMATICS COURSE

Summary:

Learning and applying programming languages is one of the key issues in implementing a compiled algorithm on a computer. However, the methodology of training individual operators in the programming language is an important consideration.

Keywords: Technology, communication, operator, circuit, computer, parameter, algorithm, software.

The use of information and communication technologies is one of the most pressing issues. Studying and applying programming languages, especially for computer-based algorithms, is one of the key issues. However, the methodology of training individual operators in the programming language is an important consideration.

In order to create motivation when starting a topic teaching, I comment as follows:

There are issues that sometimes need to be followed by specific teams sequentially when designing their solution algorithm. How to determine the best way? In addition, in many algorithms, the number of repetitions is not known in advance and is only clarified during the course of the program. What can be done to overcome this problem?

Then, I will give students an assignment on topics that they have learned in the lower grades in order to engage their students in creative activity. I entrust the students to perform this task by dividing them into groups. The students have already learned from this lesson. Immediately, they divide into groups and choose their leaders. The members of each group work together and discuss the result together.

Then I go to the new knowledge transfer phase and comment on the following content:

Constructions to create the era are available in all programming languages. You can do this by using the Python language using counter counters, conditional period operators.

Countercard. It is easier to write a periodic operator when it is known in advance how many times the body of the period will be repeated. In this case, a meter is used.

for parameter in sequence. Counter or periodic change service is variable and it is Automatically changes during installation. The first operator in the period shows the boundaries of the period.

The period is as follows:

1. If the boundaries of the period are expressed in the form of expression, then those expressions are calculated first.

2. The price of the lower boundary of the period is attributed to the change in the period.

3. The upper boundary of the period is compared to the periodic change.

4. The execution of the period is interrupted when the value of the period variable exceeds the upper bound,

5. The body of the period is in progress.

Let's say that 5 different numbers are given and you have to calculate their squares. First, let me explain.

The first operator outside the cycle is selected to absorb the starting value of the variable *i*. Preparations must be made before the circuit operator can execute.

The sequence used during the counters can also be the price increase in the cortege type.

Example 1:

```
>>> for i in (3.21, 4.63, 8.75):
```

```
    Print (i * 2)
```

```
6.42
```

```
9.26
```

```
17.5
```

```
>>>
```

For example, let's design a Python programming language for collecting natural numbers from 2: 1 to 100.

In this case, you need to know the characteristic of the range () function.

1. **Range (n) - returns a number from 0 to n (not included)**

2. **Range (n, m) - returns numbers from n to m (n is null, m is not included)**

3. **Range (n, m, k) - returns numbers in steps from n to m (n is n, m is not included)**

```
>>> s = 0
```

```
>>> for i in range (1, 101):
```

```
    s = s + i
```

```
>>> print (s)
```

```
5050
```

```
>>>
```

At the beginning of our topic, we noted that when the number of cycles is known in advance, the counter (for) is used, and in case of uncertainty, the conditional period (while) operator is used. The general rules of writing are as follows.

While condition:

The body of the era

Any logical expression can be used here. At the core of the period is a group of expressions that are repetitive. In the conditional period, the condition given first is checked. If this condition is met, the expressions that are at the center of the period are executed. At the core of the period is a group of expressions that are repetitive. In the conditional period, the condition given first is checked. If this condition is met, the expressions that are at the center of the period are executed. If the condition is not met, then the period is not enforced, and management is transferred to the next post-intervention. Execution of the conditional period is repeated as long as the condition is paid.

Example: Write a program in Python programming language to calculate the sum of 1 to 100 numbers using a conditional period.

s = 0

x = 1

While x <= 100:

s = s + x

x = x + 1

print (s)

Then, as I did in the previous lesson, I give these kinds of questions, and I ask students to set up their program. Students working in groups work freely and help each other.

Thus, I recommend that the following topics of the section be taught in this way. The methodology we offer activates students and encourages them to create information systems.

A similar method was originally developed and used for solving deterministic analytical problems and was called the Monte Carlo method. Within this method, the deterministic calculation problem is replaced by the equivalent scheme of some stochastic system, the output characteristics of which coincide with the result of solving this problem. Of course, what will happen is an approximate solution, the accuracy of which increases with the number. Then a similar

method was used for computer simulation and operation of systems subject to random effects, i.e. emerging stochastic modeling method. The theoretical basis of the stochastic modeling method is the limit theorems of probability theory. Many random events (events, quantities) follow certain regularities and are manifested in the probability distribution of random variables, resulting from the summation of many effects. The so-called restriction theorems are expressions of these regularities. The sum of these theorems is called the probability theory, the law of large numbers, which determines the stability of averages.

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